

Streamlining ML Training in Kubernetes: An MLOps Architecture with Kubeflow

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Abstract

Machine Learning Operations (MLOps) is essential for automating the deployment, monitoring, and management of ML models. By integrating MLOps with DevOps practices, developers can create automated training pipelines. This paper explores using Kubeflow as an MLOps platform and GitHub Actions as a CI/CD pipeline for training and deploying ML models. Kubeflow provides a scalable framework for orchestrating ML workflows in containers, with Kubernetes enabling efficient resource management. Containerization ensures consistency, portability, and reproducibility across environments, while GitHub Actions automates testing, version control, and deployment. A real-world case study demonstrates this architecture and discusses challenges and best practices for modern MLOps workflows.

Keywords

Edge Computing, MLOps, DevOps

1 Introduction

Machine Learning (ML) has advanced rapidly, with applications spanning many research fields. Data scientists need tools to automate model training, inference preparation, and deployment. Mäkinen et al. [9] suggest that MLOps, similar to DevOps but tailored for ML, enables automation and monitoring across the ML lifecycle, including integration, testing, deployment, and infrastructure management. Tamburri [14] identifies five essential MLOps actions: data ingestion, data transformation, continuous ML retraining, continuous deployment, and output production to end users.

Adopting MLOps requires organizational readiness and a mature foundation. John et al. [2] emphasize automated data collection, deployment, and monitoring, while Liang et al. [5] highlight the importance of continuous feedback loops for model reliability. Building on these studies, our work proposes an architecture integrating

MLOps tools, containerization, and GitHub Actions for automated CI/CD pipelines. Key features include dataset access, isolated environments, GPU support, model versioning, reproducibility, and seamless delivery to production. This approach streamlines ML workflows, improving efficiency for developers and data scientists while managing the entire model lifecycle.

2 Related Work

The field of MLOps focuses on platforms that simplify ML model training, inference, and workflow management. Mallardi et al. [7] use Docker containers for consistent environments, MLflow¹ for experiment tracking and model management, DVC² for dataset and pipeline versioning, and CI/CD pipelines such as GitHub Actions or GitLab for automated building and deployment to streamline model delivery. Venkat et al. [8] implement an AWS-based solution leveraging S3 for dataset storage, AWS Lambda³ for automated preprocessing, AWS Glue⁴ for ETL tasks, Amazon SageMaker⁵ for managed ML lifecycle, and AWS CodePipeline⁶ for CI/CD to deploy models on Kubernetes via Amazon EKS. Niveditha et al. [10] integrate MLflow, DVC, Docker, and GitHub Actions to enable traceable training, evaluation, and automated deployment for Renal Cell Carcinoma classification. Sirisha et al. [13] use Tox and PyTest for environment setup and testing, DVC, and CI/CD for reproducible and reliable model delivery. Niranjan et al. [11] adapt Jenkins Pipelines for automation with containerized preprocessing, training, and testing. Inspired by these studies, our architecture uses Kubeflow⁷ to orchestrate isolated pipelines on Kubernetes using

¹<https://mlflow.org/>

²<https://dvc.org/>

³<https://aws.amazon.com/lambda/>

⁴<https://aws.amazon.com/glue/>

⁵<https://aws.amazon.com/sagemaker/>

⁶<https://aws.amazon.com/codepipeline/>

⁷<https://www.kubeflow.org/>

temporary containers, addressing limitations in data versioning and Keras integration, while complementing it with CI/CD practices for streamlined training and deployment.

3 Architecture

This paper introduces an architecture that integrates Kubeflow, the Kubernetes NVIDIA plugin⁸, and Kyverno⁹, along with custom-developed components, to optimize ML training on GPU-enabled Kubernetes clusters located at the Edge. The architecture also leverages CI/CD tools such as GitHub Actions to automate the workflow.

Kubeflow’s key feature is its Pipelines DSL, which lets developers assign Python code to temporary containers via component decorators, including extra package installation. A pipeline decorator defines the overall workflow, typically spanning multiple containers. After execution, containers are removed, leaving the trained model as the final output.

Training speed depends heavily on host resources, with GPUs offering much faster performance than CPUs. Since Kubernetes and Kubeflow lack native GPU access, the proposed architecture uses the NVIDIA device plugin to enable container scheduling on GPU-equipped hosts, ensuring efficient model training.

It is considered a best practice to maintain separate training pipelines for each ML model. In Kubernetes, namespaces are employed to organize and isolate components of an application from those of others. In this context, the primary challenge involved enabling GPU access within individual namespaces. Although the Kubeflow documentation suggests that this feature is supported, the tool’s relative novelty results in a lack of detailed explanations and practical examples for its implementation. To enable GPU access within namespaces, Kyverno—a Kubernetes plugin that simplifies the process of writing and applying policies to a Kubernetes cluster—was employed.

Training runs on a GPU-enabled Kubernetes cluster, with pipeline submission handled by the Initializer component, which receives pipelines and triggers Kubeflow. Datasets are stored in a shared Kubernetes volume via the Dataset Registry, mounted to containers for training. The resulting trained model is by default stored in a MinIO¹⁰ volume, though a different target can be specified. The architecture recommends using a shared Kubernetes volume, created during installation, to ensure the model remains accessible to cluster containers for inference.

To simplify Kubeflow’s usage, our proposed architecture (Figure 1) provides a streamlined workflow for ML training. Users upload datasets to the Dataset Registry and commit pipelines to GitHub, which triggers GitHub Actions to build a YAML archive of Kubeflow pipelines. The Initializer forwards this archive to Kubeflow, which deploys a temporary Kubernetes container configured with the pipeline code and model dependencies provided via a Docker image. The container accesses training data through a shared volume, uses GPU resources enabled by the Nvidia plugin and Kyverno, and saves trained models to another shared volume. Supported features are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Overview of Supported Features

Feature	Supported
Automated dataset access	Yes
Automated Docker image creation	No
Containerized environments with model dependencies	Yes
Model training	Yes
Pipeline versioning	Yes
Model versioning	Yes
Delivery of trained models to production	Yes

A platform that automates the workflows above offers major benefits. Without it, developers must manually clone repositories, retrieve datasets, configure training environments, manage GPU access, and move models to production—all time-consuming and error-prone tasks. Our architecture integrates these steps, ensuring seamless model transfer to production while enforcing consistency, reducing human error, and accelerating iteration. An example of this in practice is presented in the following section.

4 Practical Application of a Kubeflow-Based MLOps Architecture Training Workflow

To evaluate the proposed architecture and its integration with containerization and CI/CD, a training workflow was conducted using the EPOS model [1] for 6D object pose estimation. The IndustryShapes dataset [12], containing RGB and depth images with annotations for industrial tools and components, was used. Originally developed for the FELICE¹¹ and SOPRANO¹² projects, it now serves as a benchmark for instance-based and novel-object 6D pose estimation in industrial contexts.

Before configuring the architecture, the training code must be containerized. Kubeflow uses Docker images to run workflows, allowing self-contained environments with all dependencies. While dependencies can be installed from a base image at runtime, this slows training for complex models like EPOS. After creation, the Docker image is uploaded to a registry (Figure 2); in our case, Docker Hub stores the EPOS image to support experimentation and reproducibility.

To install the platform, the target devices must have Ansible version 4.10 and the appropriate NVIDIA drivers pre-installed. For our experiment, a personal computer equipped with an NVIDIA RTX 4090 GPU was used. The installation scripts—along with the code for custom components and tutorials for reproducing the experimental workflow—are available in a public GitHub repository¹³. These scripts automate the setup of Kubernetes, Kubeflow, Kyverno, and other custom components.

Following the installation of the platform, the first step involves uploading the dataset to the platform’s dataset registry (Figure 1). Subsequently, developers define their own pipeline using the Kubeflow Pipelines domain-specific language, which enables the injection of Python code into various stages of the training workflow. For this experiment, the training pipeline consists of a single function to streamline execution. However, Kubeflow generally

⁸<https://catalog.ngc.nvidia.com/orgs/nvidia/containers/k8s-device-plugin>

⁹<https://kyverno.io/>

¹⁰<https://min.io/>

¹¹<https://www.felice-project.eu/>

¹²<https://www.soprano-project.org/>

¹³<https://github.com/Efficient-Computing-Lab/kubeflow-mlops-architecture>

Figure 1: Proposed Architecture

Figure 2: Docker image creation.

Figure 3: Github contents.

encourages the use of multiple containers to separate and manage distinct stages of the training process.

As shown in Figure 3, the GitHub repository should include four file types, with Kubeflow Pipelines defining the training procedure and GitHub Actions triggering execution. It is recommended to include the model code and Dockerfile alongside the pipelines. While the architecture does not support a private registry, GitHub Actions can automate building and pushing images to public or external registries. In this work, pushing to Docker Hub was avoided due to free-tier time limits, as building the complex EPOS image could exceed allowed execution time.

The Kubeflow Pipelines file first specifies the Docker image via a component decorator. It then defines training parameters in YAML, transfers the dataset to EPOS, executes the training scripts, and finally stores the trained model in a Kubernetes volume. Developers should also indicate the model version used. The Kubeflow Pipelines should also include pipeline decorator which indicates the execution sequence of functions that are using the component decorator, as well as any external dependencies beyond the application code. In the case of EPOS training, only one component used the component decorator. This function requires an NVIDIA GPU and mounts two Kubernetes volumes, one for accessing the necessary dataset and another for storing the trained model.

The GitHub repository serves as the entry point. Pushing to the main branch triggers GitHub Actions to install Python 3.10 and the

kfp¹⁴, kfp-kubernetes¹⁵, and requests¹⁶ libraries. These generate a pipeline YAML file, compressed and sent with a JSON version file to the Initializer to start training. The Initializer’s IP and port can be stored as GitHub secrets. The repository also includes the EPOS Kubeflow Pipelines file and a GitHub Actions workflow for a fully automated CI/CD lifecycle.

Resource-intensive tasks were avoided on the same machine during training. A lighter version of EPOS was trained using parameters from the Kubeflow Pipeline file to prevent overload. Similar observations were reported by Zhou et al. [15], who found that most resources in Kubeflow are consumed by ML pipelines, with GPU usage peaking during training and bottlenecks caused mainly by model design and complexity.

5 Conclusion and Future work

The proposed architecture combines Kubeflow and GitHub Actions to enable training on GPU-equipped Kubernetes clusters using containerization. It addresses the gap between workflow orchestration and automation by adopting Kubeflow for orchestration and GitHub Actions for automation, as shown in Section 4.

Several issues remain open, guiding future research. Key areas include integrating monitoring capabilities, as highlighted by John et al. [2] and Liang et al. [5], with EdgeCloud Mon [4] potentially enabling real-time monitoring of containers and host systems on edge nodes. Additional improvements include a local Docker registry to speed image retrieval and reduce energy use [6], and GitLab CI/CD or Jenkins running on edge devices to automate image creation and deployment locally. As a future extension, we plan to integrate StreamK3s [3] to automate the deployment of trained models directly on edge devices with real-time streaming support.

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¹⁴<https://pypi.org/project/kfp/>

¹⁵<https://pypi.org/project/kfp-kubernetes/>

¹⁶<https://pypi.org/project/requests/>